

Correlation between Curriculum Delivery and Awareness on IPR Components

(A study among Engineering College students in the southern regions of Tamil Nadu)

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ABSTRACT

The curriculum plays a crucial role in developing IPR knowledge among students by providing a comprehensive and interdisciplinary education that combines theoretical understanding with practical application, critical thinking, ethical reflection, and exposure to real-world experiences. Through effective curriculum design and implementation, educational institutions can empower students to become informed and responsible stakeholders in the field of intellectual property.

Key Words: Curriculum design, delivery, Information sought, Benefits received, Correlation, IPR Components

Introduction

Engineering students are often engaged in developing innovative solutions to complex technical challenges. Understanding intellectual property rights, such as patents, copyrights, and trademarks, is essential for protecting their inventions, designs, and creative works. A robust understanding of IPR can empower engineering students to safeguard their intellectual assets and commercialize their innovations effectively. Curriculum plays a crucial role in shaping the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of engineering students, and it should be given more attention to improve Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) awareness among them.

Reviews of Literature

1. **"Intellectual Property Rights and Innovation in Developing Countries: Evidence from India"** by Arora, Fosfuri, and Gambardella (Journal of Development Economics, 2001):

This paper explores the impact of intellectual property rights on innovation in developing countries, using India as a case study. Arora et al. examine how changes in patent laws and enforcement affect innovation activities, technology transfer, and economic development in India's pharmaceutical and software industries. The study provides insights into the role of intellectual property rights in fostering innovation-led growth in developing economies

2. **"Intellectual Property Rights and Innovation: A Management Perspective"**

This literature review explores the relationship between intellectual property rights (IPR) and innovation from a management perspective. It synthesizes existing research to understand how IPR management practices influence innovation outcomes in organizations. The review examines theoretical frameworks, empirical evidence, and practical implications for managers seeking to leverage intellectual property as a strategic asset for innovation and competitive advantage.

3. **"Intellectual Property Rights and International Trade: A Review of Empirical Evidence"**

This literature review examines the relationship between intellectual property rights (IPR) protection and international trade flows. Drawing on empirical studies, the review explores the impact of IPR regimes on trade patterns, technology transfer, and economic development. It synthesizes key findings and identifies gaps in the literature, providing insights for policymakers and practitioners involved in international commerce and trade policy.

4. **Hway-Boon Ong, Yih-Jian** told that their research was to examine the perception and awareness of intellectual property rights (IPR) among university students. A survey was conducted to illicit information about IPR from two private universities' students in Malaysia. It was discovered that university students perceived plagiarism and piracy as infringement of IPR. Therefore, provision of adequate information, active participation of

government bodies and university's authorities, as well as IPR awareness activities are three factors that will encourage IPR awareness among these university students.

Statement of the Problem

In today's knowledge-based economy, engineers frequently encounter intellectual property issues in their professional practice. Whether they are involved in research and development, product design, or technology transfer, engineers need to understand how intellectual property rights impact their work and the broader engineering ecosystem. Many engineering students aspire to become entrepreneurs and launch their own startups. Intellectual property rights play a critical role in the startup ecosystem, serving as valuable assets that attract investors, differentiate products in the market, and create barriers to entry for competitors. A curriculum that educates engineering students about IPR can prepare them for the challenges and opportunities of entrepreneurship. In an increasingly globalized world, intellectual property rights have become a key factor in maintaining competitiveness in the global marketplace. Engineering students who are knowledgeable about IPR are better positioned to navigate international patent systems, protect their innovations in foreign markets, and leverage intellectual property as a strategic asset in a global context. Intellectual property rights knowledge is increasingly valued by employers in the engineering industry. Engineering students who have a strong understanding of IPR are more attractive candidates for jobs in research and development, technology transfer, intellectual property management, and innovation consulting. A curriculum that emphasizes IPR awareness can enhance the professional development and career prospects of engineering students.

Objective

- To analyse the correlation between Curriculum, resources used, new delivery, and Incentives Policy and Strategic Support and Awareness on IPR Components among Engineering College students in the southern regions of Tamil Nadu

Methodology

- The study is descriptive and analytical and used both primary and secondary data
- Structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data
- 1384 responses were collected from students in their final year of undergraduate and postgraduate courses.

- Cluster sampling method is applied in the selection of sample and the districts in southern regions are put as cluster and all engineering colleges in that cluster are grouped and simple random techniques is applied in sample selection and hence the sample size comes as 1384.
- 68 per cent of the respondents is male and 32 percent is female
- 94 per cent of the students belong to undergraduate programs, while only 6 per cent are belong to postgraduate programs.
- Among all respondents, those from Mechanical Engineering (ME) comprise 37 percent. Computer Engineering and other disciplines such as Marine Engineering and Aeronautical Engineering account for 17 percent each. Electrical and Electronics Engineering (EEE) respondents make up 13 percent, while those from Electronics and Communication Engineering (ECE) constitute 10 percent. Civil Engineering respondents represent 6 percent of the total.
- 52 per cent of respondents answered, "Want to be entrepreneur," while 48 per cent answered "No."

Result on the Objective :

Table 1
Result of Correlation Tool -
Between Curriculum, resources used, new delivery, and Incentives Policy and Strategic Support and Awareness on IPR Components

		Correlations						
		Overall Awareness of Patent	Industrial Design	Trademark	Layout Design	Trade Secrets	Copy Right	Geographical Indication
Curriculum	Pearson Correlation	.480**	.471**	.559**	.606**	.454**	.652**	.531**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384
Resource Used	Pearson Correlation	.593**	.489**	.454**	.517**	.546**	.542**	.625**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384
New Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.696**	.474**	.546**	.509**	.454**	.549**	.527**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384
Incentives Policy and Strategic Support	Pearson Correlation	.498**	.580**	.555**	.606**	.561**	.443**	.648**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384	1384

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Computed from Primary Data

1. The correlation analysis between "Curriculum" and various intellectual property rights (Patent, Industrial Design, Trademark, Layout Design, Trade Secrets, Copyright, and Geographical Indication) reveals the following insights: The Pearson correlation coefficients between "Curriculum" and each of the intellectual property rights are positive, ranging from 0.454 to 0.652. The correlation coefficients range from moderate to strong. This indicates a meaningful relationship between the inclusion of intellectual property topics in the curriculum and awareness of intellectual property rights. The p-values associated with the correlation coefficients are all below 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that these correlations are

statistically significant. This strengthens the validity of the observed relationships. "Curriculum" has the highest correlation with Copyright (Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.652), followed closely by Layout Design (0.606) and Trademark (0.559). These results suggest that integrating intellectual property topics into educational curricula positively influences awareness of intellectual property rights. As individuals are exposed to intellectual property concepts through their education, they are more likely to recognize and appreciate various forms of intellectual property, including patents, industrial designs, trademarks, layout designs, trade secrets, copyrights, and geographical indications. In summary, the correlation analysis indicates a significant and positive relationship between "Curriculum" and awareness of intellectual property rights. Educational institutions and policymakers may consider enhancing intellectual property education in curricula to foster greater awareness and understanding of intellectual property rights among students and the broader population.

2. The Pearson correlation coefficients indicate the strength and direction of the relationships between "**Resource Used**" and **the following variables**: "Overall Awareness of Patent," "Industrial Design," "Trademark," "Layout Design," "Trade Secrets," "Copyright," and "Geographical Indication." All correlation coefficients are positive and moderate to strong, with values ranging from 0.454 to 0.625. This indicates a noticeable correlation between "Resource Used" and awareness of the other intellectual property rights. The positive correlation coefficients suggest that as the resources used increase, awareness of various intellectual property rights also tends to increase. The significance levels (Sig. or p-values) are all below 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the correlations observed are statistically significant. The correlation analysis suggests that there is a positive relationship between the resources allocated or utilized and the level of awareness across different intellectual property rights. This implies that dedicating more resources, such as funding for educational programs, training, or awareness campaigns, can lead to increased awareness of patents, industrial designs, trademarks, copyrights, and other forms of intellectual property. Organizations or policymakers interested in promoting intellectual property awareness may find it beneficial to invest in resources to support such initiatives, as it can contribute to a better understanding and appreciation of intellectual property rights among various stakeholders.

3. The Pearson correlation coefficients indicate the strength and direction of the relationships between **"New Delivery" and the following variables:** "Overall Awareness of Patent," "Industrial Design," "Trademark," "Layout Design," "Trade Secrets," "Copyright," and "Geographical Indication." All correlation coefficients are positive and range from moderate to strong, with values between 0.454 and 0.696. This indicates a significant correlation between "New Delivery" and awareness of other intellectual property rights. The positive correlation coefficients suggest that as "New Delivery" increases, awareness of various intellectual property rights also tends to increase. The significance levels (Sig. or p-values) are all below 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the correlations observed are statistically significant. The correlation analysis suggests that there is a positive relationship between the introduction of new delivery methods or systems and the level of awareness across different intellectual property rights. This implies that advancements in delivery mechanisms, such as new educational platforms, distribution channels, or outreach strategies, can positively impact awareness of patents, industrial designs, trademarks, copyrights, and other forms of intellectual property. Therefore, organizations or policymakers interested in enhancing intellectual property awareness may consider leveraging innovative delivery approaches to reach a wider audience and effectively communicate information about intellectual property rights.
4. Based on the correlation analysis results provided for **"Incentives Policy and Strategic Support"** and various intellectual property rights: The Pearson correlation coefficients indicate the strength and direction of the relationships between "Incentives Policy and Strategic Support" and the following variables: "Overall Awareness of Patent," "Industrial Design," "Trademark," "Layout Design," "Trade Secrets," "Copyright," and "Geographical Indication." All correlation coefficients are positive and range from moderate to strong, with values between 0.443 and 0.648. This suggests a significant correlation between "Incentives Policy and Strategic Support" and awareness of other intellectual property rights. The positive correlation coefficients imply that as the incentives policy and strategic support increase, awareness of various intellectual property rights also tends to increase. The significance levels (Sig. or p-values) are all below 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the correlations observed are statistically significant. The correlation analysis indicates a positive relationship between the implementation of incentives policies and strategic support and the

level of awareness across different intellectual property rights. This suggests that providing incentives and strategic support, such as tax benefits, subsidies, grants, or educational programs tailored to intellectual property, can contribute to increased awareness of patents, industrial designs, trademarks, copyrights, and geographical indications. Policymakers and organizations aiming to promote intellectual property awareness may find it beneficial to develop and implement supportive policies and initiatives to incentivize understanding and engagement with intellectual property rights.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Based on the correlation analysis results provided for the relationships between different factors (Curriculum, Resource Used, New Delivery, Incentives Policy and Strategic Support) and awareness of various intellectual property rights (Patent, Industrial Design, Trademark, Layout Design, Trade Secrets, Copyright, and Geographical Indication), the following conclusions and suggestions can be made:

1. **Positive Correlations Across Factors:** There are positive correlations between all factors (Curriculum, Resource Used, New Delivery, Incentives Policy and Strategic Support) and awareness of all intellectual property rights (Patent, Industrial Design, Trademark, Layout Design, Trade Secrets, Copyright, and Geographical Indication). This suggests that improvements in these factors are associated with increased awareness of intellectual property rights across the board.
2. **Moderate to Strong Correlation Strength:** The correlation coefficients range from moderate to strong, indicating a meaningful relationship between the factors and intellectual property awareness.
3. **Consistency in Significance:** All correlation coefficients have p-values below 0.05, indicating that the observed correlations are statistically significant. This reinforces the reliability of the relationships found.

Suggestions:

1. **Integrated Education Initiatives:** Develop and implement integrated educational initiatives that incorporate intellectual property topics into curricula at all educational levels. Ensure that educational materials and programs cover a broad range of intellectual property rights to foster comprehensive awareness.
2. **Optimized Resource Allocation:** Allocate resources effectively to support intellectual property awareness initiatives. This includes funding for educational programs, awareness campaigns, training workshops, and informational materials to reach diverse audiences.
3. **Innovative Delivery Methods:** Embrace innovative delivery methods, such as online platforms, mobile applications, and interactive tools, to disseminate information about intellectual property rights. Tailor delivery methods to suit different learning preferences and demographics.
4. **Supportive Policy Frameworks:** Develop and implement policies that provide incentives and strategic support for intellectual property education and awareness initiatives. This may include tax incentives, grants, subsidies, and partnerships with relevant stakeholders to promote intellectual property awareness.
5. **Evaluation and Continuous Improvement:** Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of intellectual property awareness initiatives and adjust strategies as needed based on feedback and performance metrics. Continuously monitor changes in awareness levels and adapt approaches accordingly to ensure sustained impact.

By implementing these suggestions, stakeholders can work towards enhancing awareness of intellectual property rights and fostering a culture of respect and protection for innovation, creativity, and intellectual assets.

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